

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Preoviposition and Oviposition Period of *Callosobruchus analis* on Different Green Gram (*Vigna radiata* L.)

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ABSTRACT

In India, green gram of mung dal is a significant pulse crop and has been cultivated since pre historic time. It has high protein value and easy to digest. Callosobruchus analis is a main pest of stored pulse. The adult flies were mate after emerging from pulse crop. The present study reveals the pre-oviposition and oviposition period of female beetle. The time of the pre-oviposition and oviposition affects the population dynamics of the pest. From experiment, the pre-oviposition was noticed maximum 6.12 days on cultivar IPM 02-3 followed by Pant mung 5, IPM 2-14, PKV AKM 4, Pusa 9531 and HUM 12 having mean periods 5.98, 5.25, 4.26, 4.24 and 4.01 respectively and the observed maximum oviposition 7.23 days on variety IPM 02-3 at par with Pant mung 5 (7.15 days), IPM 2-14 (6.42 days), and PKV AKM 4 (6.27 days). Rest of the varieties ranges from 4.02 to 5.92 days.

Keywords: *Callosobruchus analis*, Greengram, cultivars, metabolites, oviposition

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INTRODUCTION

Developing countries like India is one of the countries in the world which is known for its agricultural culture and the people of India from ancient times fulfil their food requirements from cereals and pulses. Pulses play a very important role in the growth and development of humans as they contain many essential nutrients required to human body. India is the major pulse growing country and also the exporter. In India, green gram, often known as mung, is a significant pulse crop, second only to pigeon pea and chickpea. India has been growing green grams since ancient times. Green gram is said to be indigenous to India and Central Asia, where it has been cultivated since prehistoric times. Green grams are a legume that is high in protein. It has over 25% protein, which is nearly three times as much as grains (cereals). It also contains 1.0-1.5% fat, ash 4.5-5.5%, Fiber 3.5-4.5% and 62-65% carbohydrate and having calorific value of 334 Cal/100g on dry weight basis. It is easy to digest (B. Baldev. *et al.*, 1988).

Typically, mungbean can suffer significant output losses due to damage from a variety of insect pests during the whole vegetative crop growth cycle. More than 64 insect pest species attack mungbean in India (Lal S.S., 1985). There are several species of pulse beetle such as, *Callosobruchus chinensis*, *Callosobruchus maculatus*, *Callosobruchus phaseoli* and *Callosobruchus analis* which damages the stored pulses crops. Out of these, *Callosobruchus analis* is most important pest from green gram. It belongs to Class Insecta,

Order Coleoptera and family Bruchidae. The pest is identified when adult beetles emerge from seeds after developing during storage. The quantity and quality of the seeds are further reduced when the female deposits its eggs on the seeds in the godowns. Grubs are the cause of the damage since they consume the entire grain, leaving only the shell.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the laboratory of the Department of Zoology at P.P.N (P.G) College, Kanpur, the current study examined the growth and development of the pulse beetle, *Callosobruchus analis*, on green gram (*Vigna radiata*) cultivars in 2022–2023. Various methods were used to record the observations and analyze the data during the experiments:

The bean beetle, or *Callosobruchus analis*, is a member of the Order Coleoptera and Family Bruchidae. Males and females are more or less similar having similar Antennae, similar pygidial median band of white setae and Lateral black spots on each elytron separated by a band of white setae. The size of the body, the colour of the elytra, the tip of the abdomen, and the various types of antennae make it simple to identify the sexes in the adult stage. In terms of body size, the male beetle is smaller than the female. Males have blunted abdominal tips, whilst females have pointy, pectinate tips, and females have serrated tips. The test insect's adult beetle (*Callosobruchus analis*) was gathered from nearby granaries and godowns of Galla mandi, Naubasta, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh and transported to the lab for mass culture on green gram, which was stored in two glass jars with a capacity of two kilograms. Twenty pairs of *Callosobruchus analis* males and females that had been previously identified were released in a glass jar with fresh green gram seeds, covered with muslin cloth, and secured with a rubber band. The container was then left at room temperature. For the creation of mass culture, the just emerged adults, who were 1-2 days old, were used as the parental population. In order to study the mating, pre-oviposition, and oviposition of *C. analis*, five pairs of newly emerged adult beetles from a pure culture were placed in specimen tubes (10x4 cm) with 25 gm of conditioned seeds of each green gram variety. To prevent the beetles from escaping, the tubes' mouths were covered with muslin cloth and fastened with rubber bands. The experiment was repeated three times and maintained in a controlled environment in the lab at room temperature and 75±5% relative humidity. Every day, a new egg containing seeds was removed and replaced with a new one. Notes on the mating, pre-oviposition, and oviposition periods were recorded for each variety.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Adults were found to mate within 3 to 5 hours after the emergence from the seed. The beetles generally mate during night hours but they also mate during day time in the dark place. The result recorded in the table below with mean values with the maximum mating period is that of 5.03 hrs (IPM 02-3) followed by Pant mung 5, IPM 2-14 and PKV AKM 4 having mean mating periods 5.00, 4.66 and 4.57 hrs respectively. The minimum mating period found to be of HUM 12 which was 3.00 hrs at par with HUM 16 (3.65 hrs) and Pusa 9531(3.66 hrs).

The pre-oviposition was noticed maximum 6.12 days on variety IPM 02-3 followed by Pant mung 5, IPM 2-14, PKV AKM 4, Pusa 9531 and HUM 12 having mean periods 5.98, 5.25, 4.26, 4.24 and 4.01 respectively.

The data was observed maximum oviposition 7.23 days on variety IPM 02-3 at par with Pant mung 5 (7.15 days), IPM 2-14 (6.42 days), and PKV AKM 4 (6.27 days). Rest of the varieties ranges from 4.02 to 5.92 days. The analysis for mating, pre-oviposition and oviposition is shown in Table 1 and graphically represented in Figure 1. The result was obtained Nikolau P. et. al (2021), controlling stored products pests with Plant secondary metabolites. The data recorded by M. Faisal1 et. al (2019) Determination of Mung Bean Seed Viability Change in Vacuum Packaging during Storage in Different Temperatures. The similar result was found by I. Nikolova (2016) Pea weevil damage and chemical characteristics of pea cultivars determining their resistance to *Bruchus pisorum* L.

Mendesil E, (2016) *et. al* noticed that the oviposition Preference of Pea Weevil, *Bruchus pisorum* L. Among Host and Non-host Plants and its Implication for Pest Management in order for the seeds to undergo a chemical change while in storage, Indartono (2011) states that seed production often takes place a while prior to the start of the planting season. To ensure that the seeds have the best possible viability when planted, they must be stored correctly to undergo the least amount of chemical change possible. To generate high-quality seeds, a number of procedures must be taken, starting with the selection of growing materials, such as seeds, and ending with a suitable facility for packing and storing seeds. The similar results were found in the study of Tatipata A. (2008). Floros JD, Ghanansekharan D. (1993) found that the ASLT (Accelerated Shelf-life Testing) method and conventional methods are the two ways to find out how long food or agricultural products will last in storage. Kusnandar, F., Adawiyah, D.R., dan Fitria, M. (2010) estimation of shelf life of biscuit products using the acceleration method based on the critical moisture content approach. Rahmi S, *et. al* (2016) claims that a quick technique utilizing high temperatures for storage can lower the amount of protein dissolved concurrently and decrease the activity of enzymes at the embryo and cotyledon in a much shorter length of time.

Table 1: Mating, Pre-oviposition and oviposition period of *C. analis* on green gram varieties

Varieties	Mean Mating Period (hrs)	Mean Pre-oviposition Period (days)	Mean Oviposition Period (days)
IPM 02-3	5.03	6.12	7.23
Pusa 9531	3.66	4.24	5.92
HUM 12 (Malviya Janchetna)	3.00	4.01	4.02
Pant Mung 5	5.00	5.98	7.15
HUM 16	3.65	4.01	4.73
IPM 2-14	4.66	5.25	6.42
PKV AKM 4	4.57	4.26	6.27
S.E(D) ± m	0.031	0.043	0.058
C.D (5%)	0.073	0.086	0.091

Fig. 1: Mating, Pre-oviposition and oviposition period of *C. analis* on green gram varieties

Comprehensive research on the identification, location, abundance, and potential for damage of insect pests that infest mung bean and haricot bean crops in the Amhara region is noticeably lacking. Recognizing the complex of insect pests related to these crops is necessary to create efficient integrated pest management (IPM) plans that are adapted to the agroecological circumstances of the area, improving crop yields and farmer incomes (Abebe et al., 2017; Tadesse et al., 2019). Conversely, mung beans are incredibly nutrient-dense, with high amounts of protein, dietary Fiber, vitamins (particularly C and K), and minerals (potassium, iron, etc.). Mung bean consumption helps prevent malnutrition and promotes a balanced diet (Rao et al., 2019). According to Duraimurugan and Tyagi (2014), the average of the preventable losses on mungbean caused by the pest complex was 32.97%, with a range of 27.03 to 38.06%. A review of relevant literature reveals that little is known about the succession of insect pests on mung beans. According to Ali M, (2006), Mung beans, a leguminous crop, will boost soil fertility and farmers' incomes, eventually replacing farmers' use of rice and wheat. Banjara TR *et. al.*, (2021) found in their study that the diversification of rice-wheat cropping system improves growth, productivity and energetics of rice in the Indo-Gangetic Plains of India. The result was obtained by Lal, S.S., (1985) A review of insect pests of mung bean and their control in India. By puncturing and sucking the cell sap from the leaves, nymphs and adults of the whitefly (*Bemisia tabaci*) seriously harm the leaves. Cupping and downward curling are signs of damaged leaves, which give them a sickly look. The plant may finally perish from a severe pest infestation. Whitefly damage started in the first week of August and continued till the last week of July (Yadav and Singh, 2013). According to the study done by Hossain, M.A., (2016) in Efficacy of some insecticides against insect pests of mungbean (*Vigna radiata* L.) found that ophiomyia phaseoli is another name for the stem fly. The mature fly takes 11–22 days to complete its life cycle and has a bluish color. The maggots of the stem fly tunnel over the roots after consuming the main stem inside.

REFERENCES

1. Abebe, A., Jembere, B., and Lema, T. (2017). Insect pests of mung bean [*Vigna radiata* (L.) R. Wilczek] and their management practices in Ethiopia: A review. *International Journal of Agronomy*, 2017, 1-9.
2. Ali M, Mungbean KS. Urdbean (2006): Retrospect and prospects. In: *Advances in Mungbean and Urdbean*. Uttar Pradesh: Indian Institute of Pulses Research Kanpur; p. 1-9.
3. B. Baldev, S. Ramanujam and H.K. Jain, (1988) *Advances in Pulse Production Technology*, Indian Council of Agricultural Research Publication. PP. 563.
4. Banjara TR, Bohra JS, Kumar S, Ram A, Pal V. (2021) Diversification of rice-wheat cropping system improves growth, productivity and energetics of rice in the Indo-Gangetic Plains of India. *Agric Res a* 10:1-10.
5. Duraimurugan, P., and Tyagi, A. (2014). Estimation of avoidable losses due to insect pests of mungbean [*Vigna radiata* (L.) Wilczek] and urdbean [*Vigna mungo* (L.) Hepper] in India. *International Journal of Agriculture, Environment and Biotechnology*, 7(4), 907-914.
6. Floros JD, Ghanansekharan D. (1993). Shelf-life prediction of packaged foods: chemical, biological, physical, and nutritional aspects. G. Chlaraslambous (Ed). *J Elsevier Pub. London*.
7. Hossain, M.A., (2016). Efficacy of some insecticides against insect pests of mungbean (*Vigna radiata* L.). *Bangladesh Journal of Agricultural Research* 40(4), 657-667.
8. Indartono (2011). Assessment of storage room temperature and packaging techniques for soybean seed quality. *Echo technology* 16 (3): 158-163.
9. Kusnandar, F., Adawiyah, D.R., dan Fitria, M. (2010). Estimation of shelf life of biscuit products using the acceleration method based on the critical moisture content approach. *J. Food Technology and Industry* 21 (2): 1-6.
10. Lal, S.S., (1985). A review of insect pests of mungbean and their control in India. *International Journal of Pest Management* 31(2), 105-114.
11. M. Faisal, U. Ahmad and D. Wulandani (2019) Determination of Mung Bean Seed Viability Change in Vacuum Packaging during Storage in Different Temperatures, IOP Conf. Series: Materials Science and Engineering 557 012074, doi:10.1088/1757-899X/557/1/0120741.
12. Mendesil E, Rämert B, Marttila S, Hillbur Y and Anderson P (2016) Oviposition Preference of Pea Weevil, *Bruchus pisorum* L. Among Host and Non-host Plants and its Implication for Pest Management. *Front. Plant Sci.* 6:1186. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2015.01186.
13. Nikolau P., Marcinak P., Zbigniew A. and Ntalli N. (2021), controlling stored products 'pests with Plant secondary metabolites, *MPDI* vol 11(9) 879.

14. Nikolova (2016) Pea weevil damage and chemical characteristics of pea cultivars determining their resistance to *Bruchus pisorum* L. Bulletin of Entomological Research 106, 268–277.
15. Rahmi S, Ahmad U, Wulandari D. (2016). Estimation of soybean seed shelf life using *Accelerated Shelf-life Testing* (ASLT). *Journal of Agricultural Engineering*.
16. Rao, B., Ramanjaneyulu, M., et al. (2019). Nutritional benefits of mung beans: A review. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 56(8), 3160-3169.
17. Tadesse, A., Assefa, E., et al. (2019). Comprehensive assessment of insect pests affecting mung bean and haricot bean production in the Amhara region, Ethiopia. *Ethiopian Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 29(1), 21-30.
18. Tatipata A. (2008). Effect of initial water content, packaging and shelf life on membrane proteins in soybean mitochondria. *Bul. Agron.* 36 (1): 8-16.
19. Yadav, N.K., Singh, P.S., (2013). Seasonal abundance of insect pests on mung bean and its correlation with abiotic factors. *Journal of Entomological Research* 37(4), 297-299.